

Simulator attempt to install in infinite loop when get "ALL_PARSE_FAILED_UNEXPECTED_EXCEPTION:" error #3

New issue

Closed

```

For corrupted APK: F-Droid_fff8d915.apk

We get infinit loop:

[CONNECTION] ADB is enabled and connected.
[CONNECTION] TelnetConsole is not enabled.
[CONNECTION] DroidBotAppConn is enabled and connected.
[CONNECTION] Minicap is not enabled.
[CONNECTION] Logcat is enabled and connected.
[CONNECTION] UserInputMonitor is enabled and connected.
[CONNECTION] ProcessMonitor is enabled and connected.
[CONNECTION] DroidBotIme is enabled and connected.
Please wait while installing the app...
adb: failed to install /users/kevenmen/ApkVulFuzz/Evaluation-SSBSE-2026/seeds/F-Droid_fff8d915.apk: Failure [INST

Please wait while installing the app...
[CONNECTION] ADB is disconnected
[CONNECTION] Logcat is disconnected
[CONNECTION] UserInputMonitor is disconnected
Please wait while installing the app...
[CONNECTION] DroidBotIme is disconnected
[CONNECTION] ProcessMonitor is disconnected

```

Assignees
No one assigned

Labels
blackbox fuzzing droidbot hang

Projects
No projects

Milestone
No milestone

Relationships
None yet

Development
Code with agent mode

No branches or pull requests

Participants

added hang last month

[F-Droid_fff8d915.zip](#)
This is the corrupted file.

3 weeks ago
[F-Droid.zip](#)
This is the original file.

added droidbot blackbox fuzzing 3 weeks ago

mentioned this 3 weeks ago
[Issues with Corrupted Apps | honeynet/droidbot#](#)

Reported. Nothing is needed now from our side; closing this issue.

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